

Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of Some Bis and Cyclopropane Derivatives of 5-Thiopyrazolones

S. DEVI, A. NAYAK† and A. S. MITTRA*

Mayurbhanj Chemical Laboratory, Ravenshaw College,
Cuttack-753 003Manuscript received 12 July 1982, revised 26 September 1983,
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It was observed in our earlier studies on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁵ that 2-pyrazolin-5-ones and their bis and cyclopropane derivatives possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. It was further noted that 5-thiopyrazolones^{6,7} were more active than their corresponding oxygenated compounds. Encouraged by these observations we thought it of interest to synthesise and study the fungitoxicity of some bis and cyclopropane derivatives of 5-thiopyrazolones.

4,4'-Bis-benzylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thiones (I) were prepared by the Michael addition of 1-phenyl-4-monoarylidene-5-thiopyrazolone with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thiones. The structure of these bis compounds (I) were supported by their elemental analysis, infrared and mass spectral studies. Their ir spectra showed bands near 2900, 1060 and 1490 cm^{-1} attributable to enolic bands, C=S groups, and C-CH₃ groups, respectively. The molecular weight was found to be the same as inferred from mass spectral studies. The molecular ion peak of the compound Ia was observed at 468 m/e. A peak at 466 arises presumably from the loss of 2H leading to the formation of a stable spiro-cyclopropane ring. Intense peaks at 434 and 433 are due to the elimination of ³³S and ³⁴S, respectively. The peak at 357 corresponds to the removal of C₆H₅ radical. Peaks at 40, 32 and 28 are attributed to the removal of CH≡C-CH₃, S and N₂ radicals, respectively.

By adding saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide to alkaline bis compound solutions, corresponding cyclopropane derivatives (II) were precipitated out. The structure of these compounds were confirmed from their elemental analysis, infrared and mass spectral studies. The ir spectra of these cyclopropane compounds showed a broad band between 3200 and 3100 cm^{-1} attributable to -CH group in cyclopropane ring. Further, bands near 1500 and 1070 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of C-CH₃ and C=S groups in these compounds.

All the eighteen compounds of the two series thus prepared were screened for their antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* by standard method⁸, using spore germination tests at various concentrations.

The fungicidal results of the bis compounds are enlisted in Table 1 and those of the cyclopropane derivatives in Table 2, respectively. It is seen from the results that the bis compounds, in general, showed higher fungicidal activity than their corresponding cyclopropane derivatives. The bis compounds (Table 1) Ia, Ib, Ie, If and Ij were active against both the pathogens. Further, all the bis compounds except Id and Ih exhibited encouraging fungicidal activity against *P. oryzae* and except compounds Ic, Ig, Ih, all were active against *H. oryzae*. The compound Ib showed maximum antifungal activity among all the bis compounds and inhibits 95 and 99% of spore germination of *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae*, respectively at 1000 ppm. All the cyclopropane compounds (Table 2) in general showed less activity against both the pathogens than their corresponding bis compounds. However, the cyclopropane compounds IIb and IIe were active against *P. oryzae* and IIb, IIe and IIj against *H. oryzae*.

From the fungicidal results of these two series of compounds, it is observed that when the substituents at R are phenyl, *o*-nitro phenyl and *o*-hydroxy phenyl groups, the compounds exhibit significant fungicidal activity. Further, the introduction of a cyclopropane ring into the bis compounds retards the activity markedly.

Experimental

Preparation of 4,4'-bis-benzylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (Ia) :

1-Phenyl-4-benzylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.01 mole) was taken in ethanol (20 ml) and to it 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.01 mole) taken in 0.1 N sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml) was added. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 4 hr on a water bath. The excess alcohol was evaporated off and the resulting solution on acidification

† Regional Research Laboratory, Bhubaneswar-751 018.

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF 4,4'-bis-BENZYLIDENE-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-THIONE (I)

Compound	R	Mol. formula	m.p. °C	% Sulphur Found (Calcd.)	Yield %	Germination inhibited % at 1000 ppm <i>P. oryzae</i> / <i>H. oryzae</i>
Ia	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ S ₂	180	13.05 (13.67)	60	81/88
Ib	<i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ S ₂ O	140	13.18 (13.32)	55	95/99
Ic	<i>m</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ S ₂ O	110	13.65 (13.22)	50	72/51
Id	<i>p</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ S ₂ O	135	13.09 (13.22)	55	53/84
Ie	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	95	12.08 (13.47)	52	97/74
If	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	165	12.10 (12.47)	54	60/65
Ig	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	80	12.98 (12.47)	50	84/57
Ih	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₄ S ₂ O	90	12.35 (12.85)	55	55/59
Ij	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	130	12.25 (12.44)	58	69/72

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF CYCLOPROPANE DERIVATIVE OF 4,4'-bis-BENZYLIDENE-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-THIONE (II)

Compound	R	Mol. formula	m.p. °C	% Sulphur Found (Calcd.)	Yield %	Germination inhibition % at 1000 ppm <i>P. oryzae</i> / <i>H. oryzae</i>
IIa	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂	64	13.05 (13.73)	50	58/41
IIb	<i>o</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂ O	122	13.85 (13.27)	40	65/59
IIc	<i>m</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂ O	105	13.99 (13.27)	35	54/30
IId	<i>p</i> -OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂ O	84	12.98 (13.27)	45	32/46
IIe	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	155	12.03 (12.52)	50	63/60
IIf	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	65	12.26 (12.52)	38	40/35
IIg	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	110	12.10 (12.52)	46	48/39
IIh	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ S ₂ O	75	12.60 (12.90)	48	28/30
IIj	4-OH-3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	150	12.01 (12.50)	40	35/57

with cold dil. HCl (25 ml) precipitated a white compound. It was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried in vacuum and finally crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 180°, yield 60%.

The compound was soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gave colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

Adopting the above procedure compounds **Ib** to **Ij** were prepared.

Preparation of cyclopropane derivatives of Ia (IIa) :

4,4'-Bis-benzylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thiones (8 g) was dissolved in 20% NaOH solution (25 ml). To it a saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide (30 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for 2 hr. The brownish compound precipitated out was filtered, washed with 20% sodium thiosulphate solution and then with distilled water. It was dried in vacuum and finally crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 64°, yield 50%.

The compound was soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gave no colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

Adopting the above procedure compounds **IIb** to **IIj** were prepared.

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Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Substituted 4-Thiazolidinones and Their Benzoyl Derivatives

S. V. PATEL, G. V. BHADANI and G. B. JOSHI*

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar-364 002

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives are known to possess a variety of physiological properties, viz., anticonvulsant¹, sciatic nerve block², spiral anaes-

thesia³, CNS-stimulant⁴, local anaesthetic⁵, analgesic⁶, choleric⁷, sedative⁸, antiphlogistic⁹ activities.

With a view of preparing better therapeutic agents, we have synthesised 4-thiazolidinones of type (I) containing nitrophenol residue by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid or thiomalic acid on Schiff bases obtained by condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro-benzophenone⁸ with different sulpho drugs. The structures were supported by ir spectra¹⁰⁻¹³.

I

R = H, pyrimidyl, 4'-methyl pyrimidyl, 4',6'-dimethyl pyrimidyl, 2'-thiazolyl or 3',4'-dimethyl oxazolyl.

R₁ = H, OH, OH₂COOH
R₂ = H, OOC₂H₅

The ir spectra of 4-thiazolidinones (I) were taken in KBr pellets. The C=O group frequency was obtained at 1630, N-CO at 1575, phenolic OH at 3415 and NHSO₂ at 1160 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro benzalanyl-2-benzoate : 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro-benzophenone (0.01 mole) dissolved in ethanol was added to sulphanilamides (0.01 mole) in ethanol and refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The content was poured into water. The product was separated and crystallised from ethanol. The anils were benzoylated by treatment with benzoyl chloride and 10% cold sodium hydroxide solution. The product was poured on ice, separated and crystallised from ethanol. (R₂ = H; yield 68%, m.p. 110°). (Found : C, 56.96; H, 4.00; N, 9.94. C₂₀H₁₇O₅N₃S requires C, 57.00; H, 4.04; N, 9.98%).

Other anils were prepared similarly. The physical constants and antimicrobial data of the anils are given in Table 1.

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-3'-nitro phenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-4-thiazolidinone : α-Phenyl-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro benzal anil (0.01 mole) in benzene was refluxed with thioglycolic acid (0.01 mole) on a water bath for 4 hr. The product was crystallised from ethanol, yield 58%, m.p. 140°. (Found : C, 54.40; N, 3.88; H, 8.63. C₂₃H₁₆O₅N₃S₂ requires C, 54.43; H, 3.92; N, 8.66%).

Similarly, other anils were treated with thioglycolic acid.

Preparation of α-phenyl-2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-3'-nitro phenyl)-3-p-amino sulphophenyl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone : Thiolactic acid (0.01 mole) was added to a saturated solution of α-phenyl-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-3-nitro benzal anil (0.01 mole) in dry benzene

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005